

The Feminization of Poverty

The majority of the 1.5 billion people living on 1 dollar a day or less are women. In addition, the gap between women and men caught in the cycle of poverty has continued to widen in the past decade, a phenomenon commonly referred to as "the feminization of poverty". Worldwide, women earn on average slightly more than 50 per cent of what men earn. Women living in poverty are often denied access to critical resources such as credit, land and inheritance. Their labour goes unrewarded and unrecognized. Their health care and nutritional needs are not given priority, they lack sufficient access to education and support services, and their participation in decision-making at home and in the community are minimal. Caught in the cycle of poverty, women lack access to resources and services to change their situation.

The Platform for Action adopted by the Fourth World Conference on Women, held in Beijing in 1995, identified the eradication of the persistent and increasing burden of poverty on women as one of the 12 critical areas of concern requiring special attention and action by the international community, governments and civil society.

The United Nations Commission on the Status of Women discussed the issue of women and poverty at its fortieth session in 1996, and proposed further action to be taken by UN member states and the international community, including the mainstreaming of a gender perspective in all poverty eradication policies and programmes. Among the agreed conclusions of the session were measures aimed at policies to ensure that all women have adequate economic and social protection during unemployment, ill health, maternity, child-bearing, widowhood, disability and old age; and that women, men and society share responsibilities for child and other dependant care.

The feminization of poverty is a change in the levels of poverty biased against women or female headed households. More specifically, it is an increase in the difference in the levels of poverty among women and men or among female versus male and couple headed households. It can also mean an increase of the role that gender inequalities have as a determinant of poverty, which would characterize a feminization of the causes of poverty.

Its precise definition depends on two subsidiary definitions: of what is poverty and what is feminization. Poverty is a deprivation of resources, capabilities or freedoms which are commonly called the dimensions or spaces of poverty. The term feminization can be applied

to indicate a gender biased change in any of these dimensions or spaces. Feminization is an action, a process of becoming more feminine. It necessarily involves changes over time or populations (comparing geographical areas, for example). Feminine, in this case, is used to mean ‘more common or intense among women or female headed households’.

Because it implies changes, the feminization of poverty should not be confused with the existence of higher levels of poverty among women or female headed households. Feminization is a process; higher poverty is a state. It is also a relative concept based on a women-men (or female-male/couple headed households) comparison, where what matters are the differences (or ratios, depending on the way it is measured) between women and men at each moment. Since the concept is relative, the feminization does not necessarily imply an absolute worsening in poverty among women or female headed households: if poverty in a society is sharply reduced among men and is only slightly reduced among women, there would still be a feminization of poverty.

History of the Term

The idea of a ‘feminization of poverty’ dates back to the 1970s but was popularized from the 1990s on by some United Nations documents. The concept became renowned as a result of a study by Diane Pearce, which focused on the gender patterns in the evolution of poverty rates in the United States between the beginning of the 1950s and the mid-1970s. It was initially used to mean “an increase of women among the poor” and “an increase of female headed households among the poor households”. This approach was abandoned because the measures of feminization of poverty based on them can be affected by changes in the demographic composition of population – for instance, the impoverishment of female headed households can be neutralized by a reduction of the numbers of female headed households in the population. For that reason, subsequent studies adopted an alternative approach, comparing the evolution of the levels of poverty within each gender group.

Poverty among women or among female headed households

Measures of poverty “among female headed households” and “among women” are not indicators of the same phenomena. Both capture a gender dimension of poverty but in distinct ways. They differ by the unit of analysis and by the population included in each group, and obviously have different meanings. There are reasons to consider both. The goal of headship-based indicators is to represent what happens to specific vulnerable groups and their families, therefore their unit of analysis is the household and the population considered includes both men and women (and children) living in these households, but excludes women and men

living in other household formations. Indicators of poverty among females, by their turn, make a complete separation of men and women as individuals, counting or not children as a gendered group in their aggregations. Interpreting the results based on individual-based measures of poverty is affected by the fact that poverty is usually measured at the household level and therefore male poverty is intrinsically associated with female poverty and vice-versa.

Evidence of a Feminization of Income Poverty

The overrepresentation of women among the income poor at a given moment seems to be much more common phenomena than the process of the feminization of income poverty. Actually, despite the enormous political controversy around the issue, there is little support to the claim that there is a systematic feminisation of income poverty in the world. Feminisation occurred in the United States between the 1950s and the mid-1970s, although some reject the hypothesis for the years after 1970 and the 1980s. Data from the United Kingdom indicates that from the late 1960s to the mid 1980s there was no evidence of a feminization of poverty.

Women and health concerns faced by them in India

Women in India face a variety of health concerns, some of which are unique to their gender and others that are influenced by societal and economic factors. Here are some of the major health concerns faced by women in India:

Maternal Health: India has one of the highest rates of maternal mortality in the world. Many women lack access to proper healthcare during pregnancy and childbirth, and often receive inadequate care during these crucial stages.

Malnutrition: Women in India are often malnourished, which can lead to a variety of health problems, including anemia, weakened immune systems, and poor fetal growth.

Reproductive Health: Many women in India lack access to reproductive healthcare services, including contraception and safe abortion. This can lead to unintended pregnancies and unsafe abortions, which can have serious health consequences.

Sexual and Gender-Based Violence: Women in India also face high rates of sexual and gender-based violence, which can have long-term physical and mental health effects.

Non-Communicable Diseases: Non-communicable diseases such as diabetes, heart disease, and cancer are also major health concerns for women in India. These diseases are often linked to lifestyle factors such as poor diet, lack of exercise, and smoking.

Mental Health: Mental health issues such as depression and anxiety are also common among women in India. Many women face stress and discrimination due to their gender and societal expectations, which can lead to poor mental health outcomes.

Lack of Access to Healthcare: Many women in India lack access to basic healthcare services due to factors such as poverty, lack of education, and geographic isolation. This can make it difficult for women to receive timely and appropriate care for their health concerns.

Health concerns faced by rural women

Women in rural India face unique challenges when it comes to accessing healthcare and addressing health concerns.

One of the primary challenges is the lack of access to healthcare facilities, which can be located far from rural villages. This makes it difficult for women to receive regular check-ups and screenings, as well as emergency care.

In addition, cultural and social barriers can make it challenging for women in rural areas to seek healthcare. Many women may not have the freedom to make decisions about their health and may rely on male family members to make healthcare decisions for them. This can lead to delays in seeking care and can exacerbate health conditions.

Malnutrition is a significant concern in rural areas, with many women suffering from anemia and other nutrient deficiencies. Poor access to clean water and sanitation facilities can also lead to the spread of diseases, such as diarrhea and typhoid fever.

Reproductive health concerns are also prevalent in rural areas, with many women lacking access to contraception and reproductive health services. This can lead to unintended pregnancies, unsafe abortions, and the spread of sexually transmitted infections.

Overall, addressing the unique health concerns of women in rural India requires improving access to healthcare facilities, increasing awareness and education about health, and addressing cultural and social barriers that prevent women from seeking care.

Health concerns faced by women in urban areas

Women in urban areas face a range of health concerns that are often different from those faced by women in rural areas. Some of the common health concerns faced by women in urban areas include:

Mental health: Urban living can be stressful, and women in urban areas are often at a higher risk of developing mental health problems such as anxiety, depression, and stress-related disorders.

Reproductive health: Women in urban areas may have limited access to reproductive health services, including family planning, prenatal care, and safe abortion services. Additionally, urban pollution and exposure to toxins can affect women's reproductive health.

Cardiovascular disease: Women in urban areas may be more likely to have sedentary lifestyles and consume unhealthy diets, which can increase their risk of developing cardiovascular disease.

Breast cancer: Urban areas may have higher levels of environmental pollution, which can increase the risk of breast cancer.

Violence against women: Urban areas are often associated with higher rates of violence against women, including sexual assault, domestic violence, and human trafficking.

Obesity and diabetes: Urban living can be associated with a higher prevalence of obesity and diabetes, which can have serious health consequences for women.

Access to healthcare: Despite the availability of healthcare services in urban areas, women may still face challenges accessing healthcare due to cost, lack of insurance, and transportation issues.

Overall, women in urban areas face a unique set of health challenges that require targeted interventions and policies to address.

The causes of the Feminization of Poverty

What causes the impoverishment of women may also cause the impoverishment of men. Therefore, what matters most to understand the causes of the feminization of poverty is not what causes poverty in aggregate terms but the gender inequalities behind poverty. In fact, since feminization is a process, what is crucial is the changes in these gender inequalities or in the factors that result in gender inequalities.

The feminization of poverty, among many other factors, may be caused by changes in:

Family composition

dissolution of marital unions, constitution of families without these unions, higher male mortality.

Family organization

Gender division of labor and consumption within the household, gender roles regulating the control over household resources.

Inequality in the access to public services or in their quality

Barriers to education of girls, educational segregation by sex, lack of women specific health attention.

Inequality in social protection

Contributory pensions systems reproducing previous labor market inequalities, lower access to pensions and social assistance by women, inequality in benefit concession or in benefit values in targeted policies

Labor market inequalities

Occupational segregation, intra-career mobility, differential levels of employment in paid work, wage discrimination, duration of work shifts.

Legal, paralegal and cultural constrains in public life

Property rights, discrimination in the judiciary system, constrains in community and political life, etc.

Women face a higher intensity of poverty than men in all nations. Poverty is a multi-dimensional lack of resources which may differ from family to family but the gender that is most exposed by poverty is females. When the families experience less or no earnings the first thing that is cut down is the requirements of the females. Fundamental causes of the feminization of poverty are single working members in the family, usually, women are given the responsibility of household and care giving which is a huge amount of work without any monetary benefit.

Unemployment rates for women are highest in India, there is a difference of 52% in the employment rates of males and females in India it's due to various reasons inequality in the availability of jobs as some of the jobs are associated with or specified only for males. There

is a notion that women only fit in the few jobs perfectly like teaching, medicine, beauticians, and designers.

Feminization of poverty is not only a consequence of lack of income, but also of lack of opportunities due to gender biases and fixed gender roles in some societies. Gender biases often deprive women of opportunities to independently pursue education or careers and are often linked to the expectation that women are responsible for childbearing and childrearing. Women's increasing share of poverty is related to the rising incidence of lone mother households.

Many factors place women at higher risk of poverty than their male counterparts. Though low income is the primary cause of female poverty, there are many interrelated sources of this problem. Lack of income deprives women of basic needs, such as food and shelter, and limits their opportunities for advancement. As women disproportionately earn less income than men, they are deprived of basic education and healthcare, which lowers their lifetime earning potential. The responsibilities associated with motherhood further limit women's economic attainment. Lone mother households, or households without a second parent or guardian, are the households with the highest risk of poverty. Female headed households (where no male is present) are most susceptible to poverty because they have fewer income earners to provide financial support within the household. Lone mother households relate to gender inequality issues as women are more susceptible to poverty and lack essential life needs in comparison to men.

Women in poverty also have reduced access to healthcare services and resources. Partly due to the toll of childbearing, women are disproportionately afflicted with poor health outcomes. Poor health reduced women's ability to earn income, and, thus, is a key factor increasing and perpetuating household poverty. Increasing health services to women could, therefore, mitigate the feminization of poverty. The education of women and children, especially girls, can create greater opportunities for women to lift themselves out of poverty and increase their social position. Countries with strong gender discrimination and social hierarchies limit women's access to basic education. Even within the household, girls' education is often sacrificed to allow male siblings to attend school.

Employment opportunities are limited for women worldwide. Women are often barred from materially controlling their environment due to unequal access to profitable and fulfilling occupational opportunities. Employment can be divided into informal and formal occupations. Formal employment is government regulated, and workers are insured a wage and certain rights. Informal employment takes place in small, unregistered enterprises. A

large proportion of women are employed in informal workplaces, reducing the regulation of their employment. This makes it more difficult for women to address workplace grievances and ensure safe and legal working conditions.

Feminization of Poverty is a collective effect of several factors, be it access to education or lack of health facilities that are available for women. Though access to education is the biggest factor, even today in many household parents think that it's better to invest in a male child than in a female child as sooner or later they will go away and be part of another family. Due to which women are not able to qualify the eligibility criteria for the job even if they want to work and sometimes, they end up with a very basic job or no job at all.

In many cases women are suggested not to work and look after the household as their husbands are in good positions, therefore, they can support them. In such scenarios women depend on their husband's income for a lifetime and have nothing of their own, they lose their self-esteem, decision making power, and sometimes entirely controlled by others. They seek permission for everything that they want to do if permissions are granted, they can pursue whatever they want to do else they just have to terminate their wishes and desires. A lot of recruiters do not want to hire females as they think that they will be having responsibilities of their household therefore they will not be able to do justice with their work. Other than these the unequal pay is also a grave concern; mostly females are paid less than males doing the same jobs. The ones who suffer the most are the single mothers, elderly women, women who have lost their breadwinners who do not have any other source of income, women who are from the lower socio-economic background.

According to UNIFEM (2000) women make up 70% of the world's 1.3 billion poor, and this figure is constantly increasing. If this issue is not acknowledged and conventional steps are not taken to minimize it, then all the programs run to empower women will be a waste because the above-mentioned problems are rooted in our system and faced by all the females irrespective of their positions in society.

An important achievement of the Beijing Conference has been the recognition by governments that there is a gender dimension to poverty. This has resulted in efforts to refocus poverty eradication policies to address specifically the needs of women, particularly in rural areas. It has also led to the introduction of a wider definition of poverty, one that not only takes into account minimum basic needs but also includes the denial of opportunities and choices.

The overwhelming majority of countries reporting on their implementation of the Beijing Platform for Action have referred to many initiatives in this area. A few examples are:

- In Uganda, there is now an understanding that only by incorporating a gender perspective in all aspects of the National Poverty Eradication Action Plan can the goal to eradicate mass poverty by the year 2017 be achieved.
- Cameroon, Madagascar and Niger have identified women as a specific target group in their national poverty eradication programmes.
- Senegal has conducted gender training for senior decision-makers to mainstream a gender perspective into sectoral development planning.
- In 1998, the Palestinian Ministry of Social Affairs devoted resources to special projects for the development of entrepreneurial skills among women.
- Denmark's development assistance policy calls for the inclusion of a gender perspective in all programmes.
- Singapore has implemented the Small Families Improvement Scheme, the purpose of which is to help low-income families to get access to education and housing.

Women and Globalization

The negative impact of the globalization of the world economy is borne disproportionately by women. As the economy becomes increasingly linked to global markets, it often leads to a reduction in public spending and social programmes, pushing the costs on to the family, where it is most often the women who shoulder the added burden.

- China has reported that due to its comprehensive approach to poverty eradication among women, the number of its citizens living in poverty has dropped from 65 million in 1995 to 42 million in 1998. Sixty per cent of those freed from poverty have been women.
- Zambia, like most African countries, is trying to cushion the negative impact of structural adjustment programmes on women. It is implementing a Social Action Programme that will provide payment for women's education and health services.
- The PROGRESEA programme, introduced in Mexico in 1997, offers assistance to poor women in the areas of employment, education, health and nutrition.
- The introduction of a minimum wage in the United Kingdom and the United States has benefited 1.3 million and 5.7 million women, respectively.
- In Georgia, an analysis of the impact of macroeconomic investments and taxation policies on women helped formulate policies to minimize the negative impact of economic transformations on women.

- In Germany, a pilot project called "Assistance for single homeless mothers" integrated women into society and provided them with employment.

Key to Change

Empowering women is a critical factor in freeing the millions of people who are caught in the cycle of poverty and hunger. By providing women with access to economic and educational opportunities, as well as the autonomy needed to take advantage of such opportunities, an important obstacle to poverty eradication would be overcome.

The provision of credit, especially micro-credit, has become a very popular and successful strategy for poverty eradication. According to the United Nations Development Programme's Poverty Report 1998, at present some 10 million women around the world are reached by systems of small loans. Among the examples, since the Beijing Conference, are:

- In 1997, the United States granted more than 10,000 loans, totalling 67 billion dollars, to women business-owners.
- In Belize, the Small Farmers and Business Bank provided 29 per cent of its funds to women.
- Japan gave interest-free loans to 27,000 rural women.
- Since 1994, 96 per cent of Palestinian women who participated in agricultural projects benefited from the implementation of loan programmes.
- In Trinidad and Tobago, the Small Business Development Company has distributed 65 per cent of its loans to women.
- In Sudan, the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) has provided seed money for the establishment of commercial enterprises to raise the standard of living of low-income women.
- In Viet Nam, a project supported by the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) has reached more than 60,000 poor women in 198 communes of 28 provinces, providing them with small loans and basic knowledge about income generation activities.

The Beijing Platform for Action also called on countries to "undertake legislative and administrative reforms to give women full and equal access to economic resources, including the right to inheritance and to ownership of land". However, progress in this area has been

slow. Only a small number of countries — including Bolivia, Malaysia, Tanzania and Zimbabwe — have changed their laws to make it possible for women to inherit land.

Female-headed Households

In both developed and developing countries, there has been an increase in the number of female-headed households. Female-headed households that do not have access to remittances from male earners are generally assumed to be poorer than male-headed households. Female-headed households are more vulnerable to increased unemployment and reductions in social and welfare spending. Actions to counter this include:

- In the 1988 Budget Law, Italy allocated 250 million lire to guarantee a basic income for poor families, most of which were headed by women.
- Iran and Japan have allocated funds to programmes that integrate rural female-headed households into productive employment.
- Singapore has implemented the Small Families Improvement Scheme designed to help low-income families, particularly those headed by women, gain access to education and housing.
- Greece has instituted allowances benefiting female-headed households.

Way Ahead

Feminization of Poverty can be eradicated by practicing equity, presenting resources for the woman, practicing gender equality in term of pay which has the main impact on what kind of life a woman is living. Once this issue is eradicated women will be able to exercise and enjoy their rights, which are exercised by only a few women today. Major aspects that are required to be worked upon are ideological changes that promote equality, create opportunities for economic empowerment of women through macro socio-economic reform.

Problems faced by women but can be seen by everyone, feminist ideologies have been in practice for a few years now promoting women's rights and improving the status of women in our society, but it is needed that men voicing their problems and encouraging others to bring the change, it is needed to understand patriarchy from a woman perspective. Deeply rooted values and beliefs that have a direct impact on gender roles need to be addressed and changed as required. Intervention programs and policies that are designed for disadvantaged women sometimes do not reach the women who need them; therefore more effective ways

should be used so that these policies and programs can be used effectively for the empowerment of people.

Families need to be sensitized towards gender roles and gender norms and new schemes. Monetary support is provided to the parents of the girl child under various schemes still only 3 out of 4 girls complete their secondary education, it is believed other than monetary support it's very important to explain the importance of educating girls to their parents. Education loans should be made accessible to young girls. Easily approachable skill training centers should be set up. Access to a medical facility for women is important. To improve the living conditions and position of the women in our society, we need to look into the embedded problems of our system, and patriarchal beliefs that are instilled in our society and rectify them so that even women can have access to their democratic rights and live their lives with dignity, and are not treated as second class citizens.

Why are women more likely to be poor?

Persistent inequalities in all societies mean women and girls are disproportionately affected by poverty and oppression. There are many complex and interconnected issues that perpetuate poverty and are a barrier to gender equality, just some of these are;

- Unequal economic opportunities, including access to livelihoods and the gender pay gap
- Limited access to quality education
- Health and nutrition challenges
- Lack of government representation
- Gender-based violence
- Conflict

However, there are also less tangible causes of inequality— and are a result of everyday gender biases present in societies and governments. Such biases span a multitude of areas, themes and levels of severity; but all result in women and girls being disproportionately affected by poverty and oppression across the world. put this into context, last year a UN report found that almost 90% of men and women hold some sort of bias against females. The "Gender Social Norms" index analysed biases in areas such as politics and education in 75 countries, covering 80% of the world's population. Here are a few of the findings:

- Globally, close to 50% of men said they had more right to a job than women;

- Half of the world's men and women feel that men make better political leaders;
- Almost a third of respondents thought it was acceptable for men to hit their partners.

The study also concluded that there are no countries in the world that have achieved gender equality.

CONCLUSION

The feminization of poverty combines two morally unacceptable phenomena: poverty and gender inequalities. It thus deserves special attention from policymakers in determining the allocation of resources to pro-gender equity or anti-poverty measures. If poverty is not being feminized, resources can be redirected to other types of policies. While accepting increasing numbers of endorsements of the nature that “women not only bear the brunt of poverty, but their empowerment is key to its reduction”, it is vital to ensure that this does not entail women becoming further mired in a situation of disproportionate burdens and unjust demands. Thinking about the ‘feminisation of poverty’ from a more multidimensional vantage point calls not only for increasing women’s access to income and enterprise, but to shore up the public resources necessary for improving the physical environments in which they manoeuvre, while at the same time tackling the unequal gender relations which permeate the ‘private’ realm of households.

Though we can safely say that feminization of poverty lacks the backing of rigorous empirical evidence for it to be an important guiding factor when studying gender and poverty, one must beware of extrapolating the arguments to conclude that poverty is gender neutral. There are 105 girls for every 100 boys living in extreme poverty, Laosnuk&2023 Vol. V Issue-1 ISSN 2581-9917 b29a across all ages. This gender gap further widens with age as is evident from the fact that for every 100 men between the ages of 25 and 34, there are 122 women who live in poor households. Gender differences in poverty rates have been observed to even out between the ages of 40 and 65, but emerge again afterwards (Boudet et al, 2018)[24]. While many observed differences in poverty rates between men and women can be attributed to differences in age and life events, human capital and labor market structures, there are still a few that require deeper analysis and investigation. These unexplained gender differences, which have been termed as ‘the poverty penalty’ by Boudet et al (2018)

disproportionately affect young women and girls up to age 30. This poverty penalty can explain why about 5 million more women live in extreme poverty across the world, more so in South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa. This tells us that there is a need to look beyond the traditional concepts that can explain the differences in poverty between women and men, and explore more areas for action to help women and men out of poverty. This would require detailed attention to theories that are supported by not only logic and observation, but also rigorous empirical evidence.